

Data management plan for project "Strengthening values-based family literacy and sexuality education in the Latvian education system"

Version 3

Description

In 2017-2024, postdoctoral research and 2 LCS projects investigated the understanding and needs of moral education in the Latvian education system. Given the lack of value-based materials for pupils' sexuality education, it is necessary to explore the relationship between moral education and sexuality and its education in the context of developing family literacy.

The objectives of the study are (1) to investigate values-based family literacy and integral sexuality education (VB-FL&SE) in the Latvian education system - its understanding, needs, and value orientation of existing materials; and (2) to explore international good practices as a basis for developing teaching materials to promote VB-FL&SE. The study adopts a survey design with mixed methods, and international good practices benchmarking. Interpretative-phenomenological analysis will be used to involve participants (teachers, parents, students) in the interpretation of the results.

The expected results are: one article submitted/accepted in WoS or SCOPUS scientific journals, a project application to a research and development call, a report on policy recommendations about VB-FL&SE policy, and the conceptualization of a school program on VB-FL&SE. The wide partner network (HE institutions, international family NGOs and governmental bodies), will have a positive impact on the UL competitiveness. Project results will be disseminated in all Latvia through the project's digital platform

Project financed by the Recovery and resilience Facility project "Internal and external consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant

"Strengthening values-based family literacy and sexuality education in the Latvian education system" No. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0011

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Recovery and resilience Facility project "Internal and external consolidation of the University of Latvia"
(No.5.2.1.1.i.0/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data management plan for project "Strengthening values-based family literacy and sexuality education in the Latvian education system"](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Recovery and resilience Facility project "Internal and external consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/24/I/CFLA/007)

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3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

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4. Templates

Descriptions

Survey of school education actors

Data collection instruments: a questionnaire with 3 sections will be used:

(1) Initial open-ended question (self-generated understanding of family literacy and moral sex education);

(2) Likert scale questions (to assess contradictory statements and definitions based on scientific literature. Approximately 50 questions); and

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(3) Open-ended and scaled questions for needs analysis and collection of good practice examples (about 8 scaled and open-ended questions).

Representative sample to be reached: at least 400 parents, 400 teachers and 370 preservice teachers from all over the country. The (valid) responses to be used in the study are calculated after data cleaning (it is recommended to collect 20% more than the minimum)

The possibility to respond both electronically and in paper format should be provided as necessary to reach the required number of respondents. Paper questionnaires will have to be entered electronically in a single Excel file.

Data collection from 21.12.2024. Submission of the data transfer by 31.01.2025.

Format: One Excel file with all responses (collected both electronically and on paper).

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Collecting data for report on policy recommendations

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No similar data available

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers in the field of education

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Microsoft Excel, Word

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-03-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2029-03-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Manuel Joaquín Fernández González (0000-0002-7088-672X)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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